

Anthracene Sulphonates as Fluorescence Probes for Triton X-100 Micelles[†]

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The emission properties of 1-anthracene sulphonate, 2-anthracene sulphonate, 1,5-anthracene disulphonate and 1,8-anthracene disulphonate have been studied in Triton X-100 micellar medium. The changes in the emission characteristics as a function of surfactant concentration have been used for locating the site of residence of the fluorescent probes in the micelles.

MICELLES, vesicles and liposomes are often used as membrane biomimetic agents¹⁻³. The importance of membrane in biological systems lies in their capacity to provide a matrix for arranging the reaction sequentially for efficient interaction, that is, they help compartmentalisation of the reactants dynamically. Compartmentalisation concentrates and localises reactants for efficient interaction. The most commonly cited example is natural photosynthesis. The components of photosynthetic apparatus are dynamically arranged in the thylakoid membrane for light harvesting, charge separation, vectorial electron transfer, water oxidation and carbon dioxide fixation⁴. Micelles serve as suitable media for demonstrating the advantage of compartmentalisation on electron transfer⁴⁻⁶ and energy transfer interactions⁷⁻⁹.

Micelles may be considered as miniaturised cages of volume v which may be charged or neutral. The surface charges reflect the polarity of the head group. The micelles are uniformly distributed in the bulk phase and form a 'pseudophase'. These micellar assemblies are in dynamic equilibrium with the surfactant monomers. There are two time constants, (i) movement of single molecule of detergent in the micelle, mobile monomer-micelles equilibrium ($\tau \approx \mu\text{s}$) and (ii) cooperative formation and dissolution of micelles as a whole ($\tau \approx \text{ms}$). The topological features of the interior of the micelles is determined by the nature of the surfactant. The substrate molecules may be sequestered and organised in the micellar interior or on the micellar boundary. The fluorescence probes have been used to provide information on the structure and dynamics of many systems^{10,11}. The effective lifetime of fluorescence varies from 10^{-8} to 10^{-12} s and that of phosphorescence from 10^1 to 10^{-6} s and hence, these luminescent probes allow scanning of dynamic properties within the time scale of tens of a second to picosecond. Much fundamental insight has been gained from fluorescence quenching experiments.

For quite some time past we have been interested in variously substituted anthracene sulphonates and subtle changes in their photophysical and photochemical properties dependent on the position of attachment of SO_3^- group. The introduction of SO_3^- group not only makes these compounds water soluble but also brings about changes in their excited state properties^{12,13}, such as emission characteristics, fluorescence lifetimes, excited state dipole moments and redox potentials¹⁴. The sulphonate groups affect the overall symmetry property of the anthracene moiety and also introduce negatively charged centres in the molecule. Thus these molecules develop regions of varied physical characteristics. The properties of four molecules, two monosulphonates, 1-anthracene sulphonate (1-AS) and 2-anthracene sulphonate (2-AS), and two disulphonates 1,5-anthracene disulphonate (1,5-AS) and 1,8-anthracene disulphonates (1,8-AS), have been well studied and were selected for further studies in micellar system.

The emission spectra of monosulphonates are sensitive to solvent. Specially 1-AS gives a completely structureless emission spectrum in aqueous solution which develops vibrational features on addition of ACN, EtOH, EG, THF *etc.* It appears that the interaction is very specific with H_2O . Evidences are that an exciplex with one or two water molecules is formed in the excited state. Fluorescence spectral studies in CTAB micelles¹⁴ have established that 1-AS can be used as a probe for water pools in membranes and micelles. On the other hand, 1,5-AS exhibits regular vibrational features as obtained for anthracene in organic solvents. With two units of negative charge, on bulky SO_3^- groups they are expected to lie on the micellar surface. This property has been exploited and 1,5-AS has been used for studying ion flux across the membranes using fluorescence quenching technique¹⁵. These sulphonates do not interact with positively charged micelles of SDS.

[†] Dedicated to Professor Sadhan Basu on the occasion of his 65th birthday.

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Fig. 1. Fluorescence spectra of anthracene sulphonates as a function of Triton X-100 concentrations: (a) anthracene 1-sulphonate, (b) anthracene 2-sulphonate, (c) anthracene 1,5-disulphonate and (d) anthracene 1,8-disulphonate; concentration of Triton X-100: (1) 0.0, (2) 5.0×10^{-5} , (3) 1.0×10^{-4} , (4) 5.0×10^{-4} , (5) 1.0×10^{-3} , (6) 5.0×10^{-3} and (7) 1.0×10^{-2} M.

For a better understanding of interaction between surfactants and the fluorophor a study of these anthracene sulphonates with the surfactant TX-100 has been taken up. The neutral surfactant Triton X-100 (octylphenoxypolyethoxyethanol) has no charged interface and can provide at least three distinct regions¹⁶: relatively polar polyether interface region, inner core hydrocarbon region and the potentially π -bonding aromatic region in the centre. The changes in the emission characteristics as a function of surfactant concentration have been used for locating the site of residence of the fluorescent probes in TX-100 micelles.

Experimental

Anthracene 1,2-monosulphonates and 1,5-, 1,8-disulphonates abbreviated as 1-AS, 2-AS, 1,5-AS and 1,8-AS, were prepared by reducing corresponding anthraquinones with Zn-dust and 20% NH_4OH for 4-6 h. The products were treated with active animal charcoal to remove traces of anthraquinones and other impurities, crystallised three to four times from water and obtained as the sodium salt. Triton X-100 (B.D.H.) was used as such.

Fluorescence spectra were recorded with a Perkin-Elmer MPF 44B spectrofluorimeter. The fluo-

rescence spectra were measured for dilute solutions (10^{-5} to 10^{-6} M) of anthracene sulphonates with gradual addition of TX-100. Concentration of surfactant was varied from 10^{-5} to 10^{-2} M. All the solutions were deoxygenated prior to mixing.

Results and Discussion

The changes observed in the fluorescence spectra of these probe molecules as a function of Triton X-100 (TX-100) concentration are presented in Fig. 1. The spectra of disulphonates have sharp vibrational features which show slight changes on micellisation but monosulphonates, specially 1-AS show considerable variation in vibrational features as well as in fluorescence intensity. In Fig. 2 are plotted variation in fluorescence intensity as a function of TX-100 concentration expressed in terms of molar concentration of micelles. The literature values¹⁶ of C.M.C. and aggregation number for TX-100 are 2.5×10^{-4} M and 140, respectively and were used to calculate the micelle concentration from the expression,

$$[M_n] = \frac{[\text{TX-100}] - \text{C.M.C.}}{140}$$

where, [TX-100] is the analytical concentration of the surfactant. Using fluorescence intensity as a

marker to probe molecules in the aqueous phase (F_w) and the micellar phase (F_m), a change in intensity is observed at C.M.C. (Fig. 2) which is sharp for 1-AS, but not so sharp for 2-AS and 1,5-AS. From these spectral data, it is possible to calculate the binding constant K for substrate-micelle interaction.

Fig. 2. Plot of fluorescence intensity (F) of (a) anthracene 1-sulphonate, (b) anthracene 2-sulphonate and (c) anthracene 1,5-disulphonate vs micellar concentration.

Determination of binding constant K : Since the fluorescence lifetimes of the substrate molecules are in the nanosecond range, the micelles may be considered as individual compartments and one can build up multiple equilibria model^{11,18} for micellisation of solute. For a given concentration of the solute and the micelles, the solute will be distributed between the aqueous phase (w) and the micellar phase (m) in accordance with the mass law expression,

where, k_a is the rate constant for the entry of the solute molecule within the micelle and k_b its exit rate constant, and $K = k_a/k_b$.

The binding constant K for solute-micelle interaction is similar to Michaelis constant for enzyme catalysed reaction and is given as

$$K = \frac{[S]_m}{[S]_w[M_n]} \quad \text{and} \quad K[M_n] = \frac{[S]_m}{[S]_w} \quad (2)$$

where, $[S]_m$ and $[S]_w$ represent the concentration of the solutes in the micellar phase and the aqueous phase, respectively and $[M_n]$ is the concentration of

micelles with aggregation number n . For a given $[M_n]$, $K[M_n]$ assumes the role of partition coefficient for the solute in the two phases. Assuming that the observed fluorescence F , of the solution is the sum of the fractional fluorescence of aqueous and micellar phase

$$F = \alpha F_m + (1 - \alpha) F_w \quad (3)$$

where, $\alpha = [S]_m/[S]_T$, fraction of solute in the micellar phase, $[S]_T$ being the total concentration of the solute,

$$[S]_T = [S]_m + [S]_w \quad (4)$$

One can solve for α in equation (3) and express in terms of respective concentrations,

$$\alpha = \frac{F - F_w}{F_m - F_w} = \frac{[S]_m}{[S]_T} = \frac{K[S]_w[M_n]}{[S]_T} \quad (5)$$

The expression can be simplified,

$$\frac{F - F_w}{F_m - F_w} = \frac{K[S]_w[M_n]}{[S]_w + [S]_m} = \frac{K[M_n]}{1 + K[M_n]} \quad (5)$$

and can be rearranged to give

$$\frac{1}{F - F_w} = \frac{1}{F_m - F_w} \left(1 + \frac{1}{K[M_n]} \right) \quad (6)$$

By plotting $(F - F_w)^{-1}$ vs $[M_n]^{-1}$, the binding constant K can be evaluated from the ratio of intercept/slope. Very good linear plots were obtained (Fig. 3) for the three anthracene sulphonates when their

Fig. 3. Plot of $(F - F_w)^{-1}$ vs micellar concentration of (a) anthracene 1-sulphonate, (b) anthracene 2-sulphonate and (c) anthracene 1,5-disulphonate.

fluorescence was analysed in this way. The binding constants K for the three solutes, 1-AS, 2-AS and 1,5-AS are 6.7×10^5 , 3.2×10^4 and $4.7 \times 10^3 M^{-1}$, respectively. Evidently the probes are bound fairly strongly in the order 1-AS > 2-AS > 1,5-AS, which is in the inverse order of their solubilities in water.

Distribution of solute molecules in micelles: It is now well established that statistical distribution of solute molecules in the micellar cages follows Poisson statistics^{18,20}. The probability $P_{(n)}$ that n solute molecules will reside in a given micellar cage is given by

$$P_{(n)} = \frac{\langle s \rangle^n}{n!} e^{-\langle s \rangle} \quad (7)$$

where, $\langle s \rangle$ is the average number of solubilised molecules per micelle and n is the occupancy number. For a concentration [1-AS] = $5.32 \times 10^{-6} M$ and $[M_n]$ ranging between 0.52×10^{-6} to $6.8 \times 10^{-6} M$, the percentage of micelles with 0, 1, 2, 3 solute molecules are calculated from equation (7) and presented in Table 1. The gross distribution of solute between

TABLE 1—DISTRIBUTION OF SOLUBILISED SOLUTE MOLECULES ACCORDING TO POISSON STATISTICS*

[M _n]	<s>	P ₍₀₎	P ₍₁₎	P ₍₂₎	P ₍₃₎	Occupied micelles
0.52×10^{-6}	1.02	36.1	36.1	18.8	6.4	57.6
1.6×10^{-6}	0.93	71.8	28.8	8.9	0.4	43.7
3.8×10^{-6}	0.16	85.8	1.4	1.1	—	15.0
6.8×10^{-6}	0.08	92.5	7.2	0.28	—	7.5

* All data reported as percentage of total micelles concentration.

the micellar and the aqueous phase, calculated from the simple expression $[S_m]/[S_w] = K[M]$, at different micellar concentrations for 1-AS at analytical concentration $5.32 \times 10^{-6} M$, are given in Table 2. The

TABLE 2—PARTITION OF SOLUTE ANTHRACENE 1-SULPHONATE IN MICELLAR PHASE AND AQUEOUS PHASE

Solution No.*	[M _n]	[S _m]/[S _w]
(5)	0.52×10^{-6}	3.5
(6)	3.8×10^{-6}	22.0
(7)	6.8×10^{-6}	45.8

* Solution number represent numbering of solution in Fig. 1 for 1-AS.

details are worked out only for 1-AS. The data indicate that for solution (7) total concentration of solute in the micellar phase is 45.3 times more than that in the aqueous phase and they occupy only 7.5% of the available micellar cages. That is, nearly 92.5% of micellar cages are empty. Calculations show that $[S_m] = 5.2 \times 10^{-6}$, i.e. most of the 1-AS is within the micelle following the mass action law given by equation (1). Therefore, the emission

spectrum obtained for solution (7) represents the emission of 1-AS totally bound to micelles.

The spectral changes observed on increase of micellar concentration are reminiscent of changes induced when increasing proportions of acetonitrile was added to an aqueous solution of 1-AS (Fig. 4a). From this observation one gets the impression that 1-AS molecules are gradually moving towards interior of the micellar core in the more hydrophobic region. The neutral detergent Triton X-100 has in effect four chemically different regions of polarity, CH₂OH head group at water micelle interface, region of polyoxyethylene chain of lower polarity, π -bonding phenyl group and the interior hydrocarbon core. But it can be established that the emission spectrum from solution (5) is a superposition of the emission from the solute in the aqueous phase and that in the micellar phase. There is a blue-shift of 5 nm when 1-AS enters the micellar phase; λ_{max} in micelle = 415 and in water = 420 nm. The fraction of solutes in the micellar phase α is calculated to be 0.78 and therefore, (1- α) in aqueous phase is 0.22. Assuming that spectrum (7) in Fig. 1 is that for completely micellised 1-AS and spectrum (1) gives the intensity distribution in the aqueous phase, it is possible to construct the spectrum (5) by point by point calculation of fluorescence intensity at each wavelength. The spectrum could be reproduced within the experimental error. This confirms that the fluorescence spectra of solution at low micellar concentrations near C.M.C. are the summation spectra of those in aqueous and micellar phase, and do not truly represent the position of the probe molecules in the micelles.

Localisation of probe molecules in micellar phase:

The localisation of the probe molecules in the micellar phase is normally attempted by comparing the observed spectral changes with those obtained for solvents of known polarity or viscosity or chemical structure. Of course there are more refined techniques, such as ¹H nmr or ¹³C nmr studies. From ¹³C nmr studies it has been established¹⁷ that TX-100 has rigid structure near the phenyl ring but the flexibility increases as one goes towards the core or the interface region. The fluorescence spectra¹⁹ of 1-AS in ACN-H₂O mixed solvents and in glycerol at room temperature and 77 K are presented in Fig. 4. It is evident that the ratio of peak heights of 1-0 and 0-0 vibrational bands of 1-AS vary in a characteristic manner in different environments (Hamm effect). The effect has been well established for pyrene as a fluorescent probe of polarity^{20,21}. The values are recorded in Table 3 for ACN-H₂O, THF-H₂O and EtOH-H₂O and dioxane-H₂O systems as well as for glycerol at room temperature and 77 K. The peak height ratio observed for TX-100 is 1.50. This ratio is not observed for aprotic solvents, like ACN and THF, the ratios are higher for ethanol and increase further for dioxane. For glycerol, it has a ratio 1.43 at room temperature and 1.61 at 77 K. The latter values are near that for 1-AS in TX-100. From these observations, one can infer that 1-AS is

Fig. 4. Fluorescence spectra of 1-AS in (a) water-acetonitrile mixture (1 to 5) in 0, 80, 50, 80 and 100% water, (b) glycerol at (1) room temperature and (2) 77 K.

TABLE 9—VARIATION OF THE RATIO OF PEAK HEIGHT $F_{1 \rightarrow 0}/F_{0 \rightarrow 0}$ VIBRATIONAL BAND OF FLUORESCENCE SPECTRA OF 1-AS IN MIXED SOLVENTS

Cosolvent + H ₂ O	ACN	THF	EtOH	Dioxane	Glycerol RT*	Glycerol 77 K	TX-100
100 : 0	1.20	—	—	—	1.48	1.61	1.50
80 : 20	—	1.06	1.15	1.59	—	—	—
70 : 30	1.25	—	—	—	—	—	—
60 : 40	—	1.03	1.19	1.54	—	—	—
50 : 50	1.27	—	—	—	—	—	—
40 : 60	—	1.08	1.28	1.47	—	—	—
20 : 80	1.33	1.18	1.28	1.41	—	—	—

* Fluorescence spectra in aqueous solution is devoid of any vibrational features. ACN=Acetonitrile, THF=tetrahydrofuran. Room temperature.

located in an environment of high concentration of ether groups and its motion is restricted. The most likely situation is for SO₃⁻ groups to reside near the

CH₂OH head groups of the surfactant and for the hydrocarbon rings to be near the dioxan like oxyethylene chain. Since in 1-AS, long axis of the

anthracene skeleton is perpendicular to the SO_3^- group, the molecule will try to accommodate transversely and perturb the micellar structure. Its motion is hindered as in a viscous solvent, like glycerol at low temperatures. On the other hand, 2-AS can align along the surfactant chain creating less problem of accommodation. The disulphonates, 1,5-AS and 1,8-AS are too bulky to accommodate within the micelle and reside on the surface without much perturbation.

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